

TEACHERS' MOTIVATION AS DETERMINANTS OF THEIR JOB PERFORMANCE IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS OF LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT: Job performance is an unavoidable discourse in workplace discourse and consideration, which can be seen as the essential workplace expectation from staff, or the most significant concept in organizational practice. In the context of classroom teaching and learning, the variables that indicate teacher's job performance are good teaching, preparation of lesson notes, proper usage of scheme of work, good supervision, classroom management, time management, interpersonal skills (listening, optimism, perceived observation skills and empathy) among others. The competency of teachers and their performance in delivering quality classroom instructions have been questioned in recent times due to highlighted weaknesses in students' performance in public examinations. The consistent reports on school subjects especially in biology, especially in public examinations (West African Examination Council [WAEC]) is not encouraging based on chief examiners' reports (WAEC Chief Examiners' Report of 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, & 2018). Arising from this report, the need for urgent interventions and research studies in order to salvage the situation for the better direct and indirect improvement in students' achievement in Biology is inevitable.

This research adopted a correlation survey research design. The targeted population for the study comprised 800 Biology teachers in public secondary schools in Lagos State of Nigeria. The study sample comprises 350 Biology teachers selected using a multi-stage sampling technique. The research instruments for the study are Teachers Job Performance Scale ($r = 0.859$) and Teacher Self-motivation Scale ($r = 0.632$). The data collected was analyzed using Regression Analysis.

Results showed that there is a direct and low relationship between teachers' motivation and job performance. Also, teachers' motivation is not a significant determinant of job performance.

It was concluded that although teachers' motivation has a direct and low relationship with job performance, it is not a significant factor for planning and improving teachers' job performance in Lagos state. Drawing from the conclusion, it was recommended that Teachers should also be motivated by giving them more incentives and making their work environment comfortable. Other teachers' factors should be reviewed and investigated to determine which one could suitably be useful for planning job performance.

Keywords: *Job performance, Teachers' Motivation, Secondary school*

INTRODUCTION

Job performance is an unavoidable discourse in workplace discourse and consideration, which can be seen as the essential workplace expectation from staff, or the most significant concept in organizational practice (Mount & Goff, 2000). In the view of Scullen, et al (2000), it serves as the prominent factor to be considered in decision making relating to retention of employees, promotions, rewards, bonuses, merit-based pay, among others. These views are considerably accurate, because the achievement of organizational goals and objectives is highly based on the level of employees' job performance. Job performance has been severally defined by researchers and authors in nearly all fields of endeavour. Motowildo (2003) gave one of the most widely accepted definitions of job performance, as the complete anticipated worth or value to a company of the discrete social episodes that a person does over a standard timeframe. Put differently, job performance is expected quality

and quantity of output arising from an individual effort on a particular job (Motowildo, 2003). Job performance can be understood as the execution or the extent of the execution of the roles of an employee at the workplace. In the context of classroom teaching and learning, Duze (2012) noted that the variables which are indicative of teacher's job performance are good teaching, preparation of lesson note, proper usage of scheme of work, good supervision, classroom management, time management, interpersonal skills (listening, optimism, perceived observation skills and empathy) among others. Afuwape (2017) emphasized that the teachers' welfare and disposition to duty in a school as an organizational weapon of productivity.

The competency of teachers and their performance in delivering quality classroom instructions has been questioned in recent times due to highlighted weaknesses in students' performance in public examination. The consistent reports on school subjects especially in biology, especially in public examinations (West African Examination Council [WAEC]) is not encouraging based on chief examiners' reports (WAEC Chief Examiners' Report of 2013, 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017, & 2018). Arising from this report, the need for urgent interventions and research studies in order to salvage the situation for the better direct and indirect improvement in students' achievement in Biology is inevitable. One of the variables identified to be the likely determinant of job performance is motivation.

Motivation serves a vital role in the life of an organization because it has potential to increase the productivity of employees, and to facilitate efficient achievement of goals. The behaviour of employees can be changed through motivation in any organization. From situation to situation, the level of motivation differs among individuals (Robbins et al 2005). Teacher's motivation is very important because it could influence the improvement of teachers' skills and knowledge, which in turn influence student's achievement (Mustafa, and Othman, 2010). Motivation according to Gewasari, Manullang and Sibuea, (2017) is the power, urge, or need, passion, pressure, or psychological mechanism that encourages individuals to achieve specific targets. Motivation could be seen as a drive to accomplish a task or achieve the desired height. Gazzaniga, Heatherton and Halpern (2016) defined motivation as the

set of processes that arouse, direct and maintain human behaviour toward attaining a goal.

From the aforementioned, the study examined how teachers' motivation could determine job performance in secondary schools of Lagos state, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 The Concept of Teachers' Motivation

An organization's success lies in a motivated workforce as highly motivated employees strive to produce at the highest possible level and exert greater effort than employees who are not motivated (Ikenyiri & Ihua-Maduenyi, 2011; Oladele, 2005). Motivation serves a vital role in the life of an organization because it has potential to increase the productivity of employees, and to facilitate efficient achievement of goals. The behaviour of employees can be changed through motivation in any organization. From situation to situation, the level of motivation differs among individuals (Robbins et al 2005). Teacher's motivation is very important because it could influence the improvement of teachers' skills and knowledge, which in turn influence student's achievement (Mustafa, and Othman, 2010).

Motivation according to Gewasari, Manullang and Sibuea, (2017) is the power, urge, or need, passion, pressure, or psychological mechanism that encourages individuals to achieve specific targets. Motivation could be seen as a drive to accomplish a task or achieve the desired height. Gazzaniga, Heatherton and Halpern (2016) and Robbins, Marsh, Cacioppe, and Miller (2008) defined motivation as the set of processes that arouse, direct and maintain human behaviour toward attaining a goal. According to Gazzaniga, Heatherton and Halpern, (2016), Questions about why people do what they do, such as: What inspires one to get up in the morning? Why do people have certain choices of foods? And so, one explains that animal behaviour is greatly influenced by motivation. Motivation guide people 's actions and behaviours toward achievement of some goals (Analoui, 2000).

From a theoretical perspective, most of the general theories of motivation present four basic qualities of motivational states. These qualities could be seen as the underlying nature of the unobservable construct of motivation which brings about the pursuance

manifestation. The four qualities as explained by Gazzaniga, Heatherton and Halpern, (2016) are:

1. Motivational states are energizing or stimulating: Individuals are caused to do something when in the state of motivation. That is motivational states activate behaviours. For instance, the desire for fitness might motivate you to get up and go for a run on a cold morning.
2. Motivational states are directive: motivational states guide individuals' behaviours toward achieving specific goals or satisfying specific needs. For example, pride or fear or another feeling motivates students to study for exams.
3. Motivational states help animals persist in their behaviour until they achieve their goals or satisfy their needs.
4. Motives differ in strength, depending on internal and external forces (Gazzaniga, Heatherton and Halpern, 2016).

2.1.2 Types of Motivation

In work and other contexts therefore, motivation is often described as being intrinsic or extrinsic in nature (Sansone & Harackiewicz, 2000). Intrinsic motivation, deriving from within the person or from the activity itself, positively affects behaviour, performance, and well-being (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Intrinsically motivated behaviours are performed for their own sake. They simply are enjoyable. For instance, students who study because they are curious and want to learn about the topic are intrinsically motivated. Extrinsic motivation on the other hand, results from the attainment of externally administered rewards, including pay, material possessions, prestige, and positive evaluations among others. Example of extrinsically motivated individuals would be students who study to earn good grades.

An offshoot from the concept of intrinsic motivation is the concept of self-motivation. This refers to doing what needs to be done without prompting, supervision, influence, or push from others (Self-Motivation Techniques & Examples, 2018).

2.1.3 Models of self-motivation

Self-motivation is best understood and measured through detailed theories and models. Different models have been proposed in previous research to explain the nature of self-motivation, such as the Self-Concept Enhancing Tactician (SCENT) model of self-motives; (Sedikides & Strube, 1997). The SCENT model proposes four motives, in the understanding of self-motivation, which include;

1. The self-enhancement motive: This leads people to elevate the positivity of their self-conceptions and to protect their self-concepts from negative information (Sedikides & Strube, 1997). Self-enhancement motive can be measured from behaviours such as preferring downward social comparison, judging oneself as “better than average” on many dimensions, defining positive traits in terms of one’s own abilities, and attributing failure to external causes and success to internal causes.
2. The self-assessment motive: This motive drives individuals to obtain an arguably accurate evaluation of themselves. People seek diagnostic information regardless of its positive or negative implications for the self and regardless of whether the information affirms or challenges existing self-conceptions (Sedikides & Strube, 1997). This motive can be measured from such behaviours like, seeking feedback about performance, creating tasks that enable feedback, preferring diagnostic tasks, and blaming self for failure.
3. The self-verification motive: This causes individuals to maintain consistency between their self-conceptions and new self-relevant information (Sedikides & Strube, 1997). This is inferred from behaviours like preferring self-consistent information and choosing interaction partners who verify one’s self-image.
4. The self-improvement motive: Self-improvement drives individuals to improve their traits, abilities, skills, health status, or well-being” (Sedikides & Strube, 1997). This motive can be measured from behaviours such as actively approaching and coping with problems, seeking information that enables improvement, practicing existing skills, and choosing to work on remedial tasks that reduce deficiencies (Silvia & Duval, 2014).

The SCENT model assumes a hierarchical arrangement in which self-enhancement reigns over the others. The verification, assessment, and improvement motives are seen as local means of achieving the distal goal of making the self-more positive (Sedikides & Strube, 1997). The SCENT model has been severally criticised for being inadequate in explaining self-motivation for several reasons, ranging from the fact that it infers the motive from the behaviour to the limitation in the number of motives to only four (Silvia & Duval, 2014).

Another model of self-motivation described in the literature is the Objective Self-Awareness (OSA) Theory proposed as an alternative model of self-motivation (Duval & Silvia, 2001; Silvia & Duval, 2001a) building on the original theory of self-awareness (Duval & Wicklund, 1972; Wicklund, 1975). Based on the OSA theory, the mechanisms of Self-Motivation include Self-Focused Attention and Self-Evaluation; Causal Attributions for the Experience of Discrepancies; and Interaction of Self-Evaluation and Attribution. Silvia and Duval, (2014) summarised that Self-focused attention can uncover self-standard discrepancies; attributions determine how people deal with the problem and how they feel about the perceived cause; and self-evaluation can sometimes affect attributions. Self-motivation thus rests in the interplay of two systems: a system that prefers congruity between self and standards, and a system that prefers simple attributional structure. The OSA theory further reinterpreted the self-motives as presented by the SCENT model for the measurements of the dimensions of self-motivation.

As motivation is essentially an unobservable phenomenon, many in the field eschewed its study in favor of more observable and describable processes. Instead, research focused on reward and reinforcement. Motivation is an antecedent condition that instigates behaviour. In contrast, reinforcement is a consequence of interaction with the goal object that presumably affects learning and subsequent motivation. With respect to organizational behaviour, such as the teachers' work environment, motivation is quite an important variable to be considered. It can be perceived as the willingness to put in differing levels effort toward organizational goals in order to satisfy some individual needs (Gewasari, Manullang & Sibuea, 2017).

In line with this organisational perspective, Serrat (2009) presented a model for self-motivation, which includes four competences, as part of a broader model for emotional intelligence. The four competences and their indicators include:

1. Achievement drive: being results-oriented; Setting challenging standards and taking systematic risks; and seeking improvement
2. Commitment: being ready sacrificial/selfless in pursuance of goals; and sticking to agreed paths and purposes
3. Initiative: being constructively opportunistic; going the extra mile to achieve goals; and mobilizing others through unusual, enterprising efforts
4. Optimism Individuals with this competence: Persistence; hopefulness; and positivism (Serrat, 2009).

The Serrat (2009) model will be used to measure self-motivation in the present study. As a result of the stressful nature of the teaching profession as discussed, teachers are often times poorly motivated by their work environment and conditions. Adelabu (2005) found in Nigeria that teacher's motivation is very poor and teachers are also dissatisfied with their working environment and salary conditions. The various stressors in the teaching profession including low income as compared to other professionals, poor work environment, no decision-making authority, and little opportunities for self-development among others have been identified as the major causes of teachers' poor motivation.

2.1.4. The Concept of Teachers' Job Performance

Job performance is an unavoidable discourse in workplace discourse and consideration, which can be seen as the essential workplace expectation from staff, or the most significant concept in organizational practice (Mount & Goff, 2000). In the view of Scullen, et al (2000), it serves as the prominent factor to be considered in decision making relating to retention of employees, promotions, rewards, bonuses, merit-based pay, among others. These views are considerably accurate, because the achievement of organisational goals and objectives is highly based on the level of employees' job performance. Job performance has been severally defined by researchers and authors in nearly all fields of endeavour. Motowildo (2003) gave one

of the most widely accepted definitions of job performance, as the complete anticipated worth or value to a company of the discrete social episodes that a person does over a standard timeframe. Put differently, job performance is expected quality and quantity of output arising from an individual effort on a particular job. (Motowildo, 2003).

Other definitions include those of Olaniyan (1999) who described performance as the ability to skilfully combine appropriate behaviour towards the accomplishment of organizational objectives and goals. Vigoda (2000) defined job performance as how well individuals perform their jobs in relation to standards. Hassan, *et. al.* (2010) opined that job performance regarded as the employees' capacity to achieve business related objectives and expected results in relations to specific foreordained work guidelines. These definitions sound rather directional, as they imply a positive nature for the word performance, and possibly suggest that inability of employees to discharge their duties as supposed would be termed lack of job performance. Similarly, job performance has been described by Ismail et al., (2009) as the employee's ability to achieve their respective work aims, or meet their own expectations, benchmarks and achieving or accomplishing their organizational objectives. In simple terms, the whole performance that an employee is involved with at the workplace is termed as job performance (Jex, 2002).

Work performance often depends on the support, advice, and other resources provided by others (Seibert, et al, 2001). Carmeli (2003) stressed that employees with a high level of intelligence can manage their emotions in terms of retaining a positive mental state which can lead to improved job performance (Mohamad, & Jais, 2016). According to Job performance can be determined by three factors, which are: effort, skill and the nature of work conditions. According to Peters and O'Connor (1980) effort has to do with how much the employee puts forth in work in order to get the job done; skills encompass employees' abilities, knowledge and competencies; and the nature of the work condition is the degree to which transformation of these conditions is increasing the employees' productivity (Amarneh, *et. al.*, 2010).

As expected, since different kinds of role playing are peculiar to different kinds of jobs or occupations, job performance in specific activity related terms will differ among jobs. With regard to the teaching profession, Teachers' job performance can be defined as the actions teachers perform in schools in order to achieve educational goals (Hwang et al., 2017). Job performance of teachers can be measured from multiple sources as seen by Hanif, (2010) argument that a good teacher not only teaches in a way that satisfies the class with their outstanding teaching skill or style. In addition, they must be good time managers, efficiently carrying along other duties assigned to them apart from teaching such as ethics management and discipline in class, motivating their students, ensuring students' interaction, and maintaining a proper link with the students' parents and school administration. This would enhance not only the performance of teachers but also the students' performance as well. More specifically, in the context of classroom teaching and learning, Duze (2012) gave a more summarised list of variables associated with teachers' job performance to include, effective teaching, preparation of lesson note, effective use of scheme of work, effective supervision, classroom management, time management, interpersonal skills (listening, optimism, perceived observation skills and empathy) among others.

Several studies on teacher job performance have utilized the above-mentioned variables and several others as indicators of teacher job performance. For instance, Baluyos, *et. al.*, (2019) in their study on teachers' job satisfaction and work performance utilized pupils' outcomes, teaching-learning process, community involvement and professional growth and development as indicators of teachers' job performance. The authors reported that the overall performance of teachers was an index of how well they discharged their duties as seen through pupils' outcomes, the teaching-learning process, initiating activities that promote parents and community members' participation, and in updating themselves through attending seminars, workshops, and conferences. Den, *et. al.*, (2017) measured teachers' job performance in terms of only three components: Management Skills, Discipline and Regularity, and Interpersonal Skills. While Osagie and Akinlosotu (2017) made use of the Annual Performance Evaluation Report (APER) form, which focuses on ten basic job functions of a teacher, in their measurement of teachers' job performance in their study. The ten basic functions are: lesson planning lessons, teaching lessons,

evaluation of lessons, classroom management, handling of student discipline and attendant problems, interest in teaching pupils, knowledge of subject matter, professional preparation and scholarship, professional characteristics and effort toward improvement when needed.

Some other researchers like Li, *et. al.*, (2018) measured Teachers' job performance using the popular job performance scale which was originally developed by Motowidlo and Van Scotter (1994). The 14-item instrument measures self-rated job performance, based on aspects of an individual's task and contextual performance in the work environment. Similar to the Job performance scale of Motowidlo and Van Scotter, other researchers like Arthi, and Sumathi, (2016); Sambu, (2019) used the 16-item version of the job performance scale by Goodman and Svyantek, (1999).

Several studies have as well related teachers' job performance with an increasing number of variables, ranging from personal variables to environmental variables to variables associated with others such as students and school managerial staff. Salingkat, (2017) used such indicators as lesson planning to measure teacher's performance and found that the qualification of teachers did not guarantee an increase in the teachers' teaching performance. Huda, *et. al.*, (2018) found that the variables competence, motivation, and innovativeness had a positive and significant impact on performance variables in Central Java province, with competence being the most dominant factor affecting the performance and innovation of mathematics teachers. In their study of several factors that would impact on teachers' job performance, Sutriyantono and Rubin (2013), reported that teachers' performance improved through attitude modification, work motivation, and favourable organizational culture in schools. A study conducted in public primary schools in Calabar investigated the influence of head teachers' managerial behaviours such as decision-making strategy, communication skills and leadership style on teachers' task performance. The study concluded that Proper managerial behaviours that can boost teachers' morale towards high task performance should be adopted (Mbon, 2017).

Structural relationships among learning-organization culture, self-efficacy, work engagement, and job performance in Korean workforce institutions were conducted. Teachers' self-efficacy positively affected their work engagement and job

performance, and the relationship between work engagement and job performance was statistically significant. Also identified were the mediating roles of self-efficacy and work engagement on the relationships between the learning-organization culture of workforce-education schools and the teachers' job performance (Song, *et. al.*, 2018). Other variables that can be found in the literature, though to a sparing extent compared with the ones highlighted in the foregoing include emotional intelligence (Ahmed *et. al.*, 2016; Arthi, & Sumathi, 2016; Mohamad, & Jais, 2016; Sambu, 2019), Job stress (Blix, *et. al.*, 1994; Koslowsy, 1998; Kyriacou, *et. al.*, 2004; Wilson, 2002), Job anxiety (Anusiem & Okoiye, 2015; Aslrasouli, & Vahid, 2014; Egaga, *et. al.*, 2015), Motivation (Gewasari, *et. al.*, 2017; Nwosu, 2015) and social skills (Tapia-Gutierrez, & Cubo-Delgado, 2015; Ukala, 2019) among others.

To further modify the quantification of teachers' job performance, Katz and Kahn's (1978) conceptualized the construct in terms of in-role and extra-role behaviour in accordance with the Role Behaviour Theory. In their model, in-role behaviour is "behaviour that falls under standard rules in the workplace of an organization," and extra-role behaviour represents "the self-evaluative and democratic behaviour that is accepted within the organization" (Tseng & Huang, 2011). As seen in most studies, under these and similar frameworks, job/work performance relies on the support and resources provided by other members (Seibert, et al 2001). High-performance work systems directly and indirectly influence teachers' in-role performance and extra-role behaviour through the mediation of the quality of working life. With quality of working life defined here as an essential conduit of the relationships between high-performance work systems and employee's work behaviours (Shen, *et. al.*, 2014).

2.2 Empirical review on Motivation and Job Performance

Several studies have investigated intrinsic versus extrinsic (autonomous vs. controlled extrinsic) motivation in teaching contexts, in relation to teachers' interest in classroom instruction and the subject of instruction, as well as goal orientations and as well as teacher enthusiasm (Hanfstingl, Andreitz, Mu'ller, & Thomas, 2010; Long & Woolfolk Hoy, 2006; Nitsche, Dickhauser, Fasching, & Dresel, 2011; Pelletier, Se'guin-Le'vesque, & Legault, 2002). Generally, findings from such studies suggest that teachers who demonstrate more self-determination and intrinsic

motivation tend to provide better support and opportunities for autonomy in their students and are also more effective in promoting students' motivation for learning and achievement.

Motivation has been linked with several other variables in the teaching and learning industry. According to Dai and Sternberg (2004) for instance, high levels of job dissatisfaction, stress, and burnout can negatively influence motivation and job performance. Michaelowa (2002) in her study on analysis of the key determinants of teacher's motivation in the developing country context, found that large class size, double-shifting, rural location, high educational attainment and active parental involvement negatively correlated with teacher job satisfaction in these countries. According to Bandura (1977), motivation is determined by people's judgments of their capability to execute particular courses of action (called efficacy expectations) and their beliefs about the likely consequences of those actions (called outcome expectations).

Nwosu, (2015) investigated motivation and teachers' performance in selected secondary schools in Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State. The descriptive survey research made use of 187 teachers which were randomly selected. The researcher argued that the development of motivation strategies has an important role in motivating workforce to deliver high levels of performance, discretionary effort and contribution. The results of the study reveal a significant positive relationship between teachers' job performance and motivation in ensuring quality education in secondary schools. It was therefore concluded that the importance of motivation in the day-to-day performance of teachers cannot be overemphasized, especially when it comes to being rewarded for a job done and being happy on the job.

Gewasari, Manullang and Sibuea, (2017) similarly conducted research aimed at revealing the determinant factors that affect Teacher Competence in Public Senior High School in Deli Serdang District, India. The study used a Path analytical approach, with a sample of 284 of Public Senior High School teachers. The results revealed that Achievement Motivation and the other variables (Teacher Competence, Principal Pedagogical Leadership, School Spiritual Organizational Culture, Job

Satisfaction of Teacher Development) effect significantly either directly or indirectly toward Teacher Performance of Public Senior High School in Deli Serdang District.

Mashaqbah, (2018) conducted a study to identify the relationship between motivation and job satisfaction among teachers of public schools in Mafrq Province of Jordan. The study which involved a sample of 1260 public school teachers utilized a questionnaire survey. The research has shown that: the degree of motivation among teachers of public schools in Mafrq Province is medium, as well as the degree of job satisfaction. Also, there was a statistically significant relationship between motivation and job satisfaction among teachers. The study showed that there is a lack of material incentives and bonuses, lack of a clear system of motivation that really measures the performance of the teachers, and lack of involvement of the teacher in decision-making. The researcher suggests that in order to achieve a high and distinguished performance among the teachers, educational officials should consider working on the development of the laws, regulations and instructions of the system of bonuses and rewards commensurate with the requirements of the basic standard of living of the employees.

On the other hand, Mohamed, (2013) studied the influence of motivation on job performance among primary school teachers in public schools in Kongwa district council Dodoma, Tanzania. The study, using a sample of 100 respondents identified motivation factors to include: in-service training attendance, housing provision, promotion from one grade to another, and teacher-student ratio. Results of the study revealed that the provision of the studied motivational factors was relatively not such good, and that there was no significant difference between those who attended in-service training and those who did not; those who were given houses by their employers and the ones who were not; those who had been promoted from one grade to another and those who had not in their job performances. The study concluded that there was no statistically significant relationship between motivational factors and teachers' job performance due to the variables used in the study.

Most of the studies investigating motivation in relation to other variables in the teaching context have dwelt within the domains of extrinsic motivation, especially as touching provision made by employers for the benefit of employees, such as

incentives, and other working conditions. Asiago et al. (2015) conducted a survey to explore the impact of non-financial incentives (which have been a comfortable working environment, setting up outstanding standards for promotion and including years of experience and regularity of work) on job satisfaction among high school teachers at Casey schools in the Kenyan Republic. The study sample was made up of 83 teachers, who were randomly selected. The study revealed a positive relationship between non-financial incentives and job satisfaction among teachers. The results of the study revealed a significant impact of non-financial incentives on job satisfaction among teachers.

In terms of self-motivation, there are very few studies, probably due to the lack of consensus on the appropriate model for measuring the construct. Among the few available studies, Zimmerman, Bandura and Martinez-Pons, (1992) studied the causal role of students' self-efficacy beliefs and academic goals in self-motivated academic attainment, using path analysis. Results of the study revealed that students' beliefs in their efficacy for self-regulated learning affected their self-motivated academic goals and their final academic achievement. Self-regulation of motivation, as the authors termed it, was therefore related to several other personal variables, such as self-efficacy (confidence) self-esteem, self-regulation, as well as achievements.

METHODOLOGY

This research adopted a correlation survey research design. It involves determining the existing relationships between two or more variables; also, it determines the prediction of a variable using other variables regarded as predictors.

The targeted population for the study comprised eight hundred (800) Biology teachers in public secondary schools in Lagos State of Nigeria.

The study sample comprises three hundred and fifty (350) Biology teachers in public secondary schools in Lagos State selected using a multi-stage sampling technique.

The research instruments for the study are Teachers Job Performance Scale (TJPS) and Teacher Self-motivation Scale (TSMS). For Teachers Job Performance Scale (TJPS), it is a 25 item questionnaire with four response options; adapted from the

TJPS developed by Hanif and Pervez (2004) and designed to measure teachers' job performance. The reliability of TJPS was determined by administering it on 40 Biology teachers outside the sample coverage. Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient was computed and yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.859. Furthermore, Teacher Self-motivation Scale (TSMS) is a 16-item questionnaire with four response options, which was adapted from Serrat (2009). It was designed to measure Teachers' motivation. The reliability of TSMS was determined by administering it on 40 Biology teachers outside the sample coverage. Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient was computed and yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.632. The data collected was analysed using Regression Analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

Research Question 1: There is no significant relationship between teachers' motivation and Job Performance.

Table 1: Correlation analysis between teachers' motivation and Job Performance

Variables	N	R	P
Self-motivation * Job Performance	350	0.011	0.421

Table 1 presents the relationship between teachers' motivation and Job Performance. From the table, there is no significant relationship between teachers' motivation and Job Performance (N=350, $r = 0.011$, $p > 0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis is retained. Also, there is a low and direct relationship between teachers' motivation and Job Performance ($r = 0.011$).

HO₁: Teachers' motivation is not a significant determinant of Job Performance.

Table 2: ANOVA analysis of job performance prediction using Teachers' motivation

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	10.114	1	10.114	0.039	0.843
	Residual	89160.274	348	256.208		
	Total	89170.389	349			
R = 0.11; R square = 0.000						

Table 2 presents the prediction of teachers' Job Performance using their motivation. From the table, the result showed no significant outcome ($R = 0.11$, $F_{(1, 348)} = 0.039$, $P > 0.05$). It means teachers' motivation is not a significant determinant of Job Performance. Hence, the null hypothesis is retained.

4.2 Discussion

From the first result, there is no significant relationship between teachers' motivation and Job Performance. Also, the relationship between teachers' motivation and job performance is a low and direct. The study supports the reports of Mohamed (2013), Asiago et al. (2015), Gewasari, Manullang and Sibuea (2017) where it was revealed that there is a positive relationship between motivation and job performance among teachers. However, the result contradicts the report of Nwosu (2015) and Mashaqbah (2018) where it was revealed that there is a statistically significant relationship between motivation and job performance among teachers. The association or relationship between teachers' motivation and Job Performance is very crucial to bringing out the best from the teachers through their performance since teachers are the implementer of the curriculum, managing and controlling the teaching and learning process in school.

Secondly, teachers' motivation is not a significant determinant of Job Performance. The study contradicts the reports of Gewasari, Manullang and Sibuea (2017) where it was revealed that Achievement Motivation had a significant direct or indirect effect on teachers' performance. In order to achieve a high and distinguished performance among the teachers, motivation alone is not a significant factor. Other teachers' factors must be considered if teachers' performance needs to be improved and maximized.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

The study investigated how teachers' motivation could serve as a determinant of their job performance in secondary schools of Lagos state, Nigeria. Based on the result, there is a direct and low relationship between teachers' motivation and job

performance. Also, teachers' motivation is not a significant determinant of job performance. It means that although teachers' motivation has a direct and low relationship with job performance, it is not a significant factor for planning and improving teachers' job performance in Lagos state.

5.2 Recommendation

1. Teachers should also be motivated by giving them more incentives and making their work environment comfortable so that it could improve job performance
2. Other teachers' factors should be reviewed and investigated to determine which one could suitably be useful for planning job performance

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